

The Einstein's Kinetic Energy: Is it valid?

Chinnaraji Annamalai
School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India
Email: anna@iitkgp.ac.in
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0992-2584>

Abstract: Albert Einstein found that the mass-energy equivalence of a body whose velocity approaches the speed of light, is equal to the sum of kinetic energy and rest-mass energy of the object. But the author of this article finds that the Einstein's kinetic energy is not valid.

Keywords: relativistic motion, non-zero mass, kinetic energy, rest mass energy

1. Introduction

Light waves [1-3] are generally electromagnetic and do not require a medium for their propagation. Thus, the light can travel in a vacuum. Quanta of light are the smallest discrete packets of electromagnetic energy. A quantum of light that has no mass is called a photon. The relativistic motion [4-10] of a particle is concerned with the motion of the particle whose velocity approaches the speed of light [11-14].

2. Einstein's Kinetic Energy

Let us consider a body with rest-mass m_0 and relativistic mass m ; c is the speed of light. Then,

$$m = \frac{m_0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}. \text{ In this case, if } v = 0, \text{ then } m = m_0. \text{ Also, if } v > 0, \text{ then } m > m_0.$$

Thus, when v tends to c , m continuously increases rather than m_0 . It contradicts with the following statement: "When a body releases the energy in the form of radiation, its mass diminishes by its release of energy.

Therefore, the Einstein's kinetic energy $(K) = mc^2 - m_0c^2 = (m - m_0)c^2$, and $m \leq m_0$.

In this case, if $m = m_0$, the Einstein's kinetic energy $(K) = 0$ and

if $m < m_0$, the mass of the object is a negative numerical value. For example, the mass of the object is -5 kg .

As a result, the author of this article concludes that the Einstein's kinetic energy [15-20] is not valid.

3. Conclusion

In this article, the author has justified that the Einstein's kinetic energy is not valid. This new idea can enable the researchers for further involvements in the scientific research and development.

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